

CLINICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTIMICROBIAL-RESISTANT GRAM-NEGATIVE PATHOGENS ISOLATED FROM HOSPITALIZED AND OUTPATIENT POPULATIONS

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Abstract

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Emergence of antimicrobial resistance in Gram-negative bacteria is a major threat to effective clinical settings, especially in that management where empirical use of antibiotics is common. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are among the most frequently isolated pathogens and clinically pathogens worldwide. These pathogens are frequently implicated in both hospital and community-acquired infections, including, wound infections, urinary tract infections (UTIs), blood stream infections, and severe infections in persons that have weak immunity. Current study has determined the antimicrobial

susceptibility patterns of *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae* isolated from 200 clinical that were processed in microbiology laboratory of the Department of Microbiology, Abbottabad University of Science and Technology. Bacterial isolation and identification were performed using standard microbiological techniques. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was carried out using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar, and results were interpreted according to clinical laboratory standards guidelines. Demographic and clinical data, including age, gender, hospitalization status, prior antibiotic use, and presence of indwelling medical devices, were analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using the chi-square test, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant. Of the 200 samples analyzed, 168 (84%) yielded bacterial growth. *E. coli* was the most frequently isolated organism (44%), followed by *P. aeruginosa* (31%) and *K. pneumoniae* (25%). High levels of resistance were observed against commonly used antibiotics, with *P. aeruginosa* showing the highest proportion of multidrug-resistant isolates. Multidrug resistance was significantly associated with prolonged hospitalization, diabetes mellitus, prior antibiotic exposure, and the presence of indwelling devices (p < 0.05). The study demonstrates a substantial burden of multidrug-resistant *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae* in clinical samples. *P. aeruginosa* exhibited the highest level of multidrug resistance, followed by *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli*. These findings underscore the

importance of routine antimicrobial susceptibility testing, rational antibiotic use, and strengthened antimicrobial stewardship programs to mitigate the spread of resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as one of the most serious threats to global health, undermining decades of progress in the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases. The growing prevalence of resistant bacterial pathogens has led to prolonged hospital stays, increased healthcare costs, and higher mortality rates, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where diagnostic and therapeutic resources are limited (Aiesh et al., 2024). Gram-negative bacteria pose a unique challenge in this regard due to their complex cell envelope, intrinsic resistance mechanisms, and ability to rapidly acquire and disseminate resistance genes. Among these, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are of particular clinical importance because of their frequent involvement in severe infections and their escalating resistance to commonly used antimicrobial agents (Handa et al., 2024).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an opportunistic, non-fermenting Gram-negative bacillus that is widely distributed in natural and hospital environments. It is a leading cause of healthcare-associated infections, including ventilator-associated pneumonia, bloodstream infections, burn wound infections, and complicated urinary tract infections (Alali, AlFouzan, & Dhar, 2021). The organism is especially problematic in immunocompromised individuals and patients with prolonged hospital or intensive care unit stays. One of the most concerning characteristics of *P. aeruginosa* is its intrinsic resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, which is attributed to low outer membrane permeability, multidrug efflux pumps, and the production of chromosomally encoded β -lactamases (Shi & Xie, 2023). In addition, the ability of *P. aeruginosa* to form biofilms on medical devices and damaged tissues significantly enhances its survival and resistance to antimicrobial therapy, often resulting in chronic and recurrent infections (Beyene, Bitew, Fantew, Mihret, & Evans, 2019).

The clinical management of *P. aeruginosa* infections is further complicated by its remarkable capacity to develop acquired resistance during the course of treatment. Exposure to antipseudomonal

antibiotics can select for resistant mutants, leading to therapeutic failure and limited treatment options. Resistance to carbapenems, fluoroquinolones, and aminoglycosides has been increasingly reported worldwide, posing a serious challenge to clinicians (Tilahun, 2022). In settings with limited access to advanced antimicrobial agents and robust infection control programs, infections caused by resistant *P. aeruginosa* are associated with poor clinical outcomes. Continuous surveillance of its antimicrobial susceptibility patterns is therefore essential to guide empirical therapy and optimize patient management (Mumbole & Nakazwe, 2025).

Escherichia coli are a facultative anaerobic Gram-negative bacillus that normally inhabits the human gastrointestinal tract. Despite its commensal role, *E. coli* is the most common bacterial pathogen isolated from clinical specimens and is a major cause of community- and hospital-acquired infections (Mumbole & Nakazwe, 2025). It is the leading etiological agent of urinary tract infections and is also frequently implicated in septicemia, intra-abdominal infections, neonatal meningitis, and wound infections. The global rise of multidrug-resistant *E. coli* has significantly altered the clinical landscape, particularly with the emergence of strains producing extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) and carbapenemas (Mitiku et al., 2022).

ESBL-producing *E. coli* exhibit resistance to third-generation cephalosporins and are often co-resistant to other antibiotic classes, such as fluoroquinolones and aminoglycosides, thereby limiting treatment options. The spread of resistant *E. coli* is facilitated by the horizontal transfer of resistance genes through plasmids and other mobile genetic elements. In many regions, inappropriate antibiotic use, self-medication, and inadequate regulatory oversight have contributed to the rapid dissemination of resistant strains in both community and healthcare settings. Infections caused by resistant *E. coli* are associated with delayed appropriate therapy, increased risk of complications, and greater healthcare utilization, underscoring the need for updated local resistance data (Tanni et al., 2025).

Klebsiella pneumoniae is an encapsulated Gram-negative bacillus belonging to the Enterobacterales order and is a prominent cause of nosocomial infections. It is commonly associated with pneumonia, bloodstream infections, urinary tract infections, and infections related to invasive medical devices

(Mumbole & Nakazwe, 2025). The polysaccharide capsule of *K. pneumoniae* plays a critical role in its virulence by protecting the bacterium from host immune defenses and facilitating persistence within the host. Over the past decade, *K. pneumoniae* has gained particular attention due to the global emergence of multidrug-resistant and carbapenem-resistant strains (Forouzani et al., 2023).

Carbapenem-resistant *K. pneumoniae* represents a serious public health concern because carbapenems are often considered last-line agents for treating severe Gram-negative infections. Resistance in this organism is primarily mediated by the production of carbapenemases, often in combination with other mechanisms such as porin loss and efflux pump overexpression (Baral et al., 2025). Infections caused by resistant *K. pneumoniae* are associated with high mortality rates and limited therapeutic alternatives, especially in critically ill patients. The rapid spread of these strains within healthcare facilities highlights the importance of strict infection control measures and antimicrobial stewardship programs (Donkor et al., 2023).

In developing countries such as Pakistan, the burden of antimicrobial resistance is further compounded by limited laboratory capacity, delayed diagnosis, and inconsistent surveillance systems (Safdar et al., 2025). The lack of comprehensive and up-to-date data on the antimicrobial susceptibility profiles of key Gram-negative pathogens hampers evidence-based clinical decision-making and effective policy formulation. Local epidemiological studies are therefore crucial to identify prevailing resistance patterns and guide empirical treatment strategies.

The present study was undertaken to investigate the distribution and antimicrobial resistance profiles of *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae* isolated from clinical specimens. By analyzing susceptibility patterns in conjunction with patient demographic data and relevant clinical variables, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the local resistance landscape. The findings are expected to support rational antibiotic use, strengthen antimicrobial stewardship efforts, and contribute to improved infection control practices, ultimately reducing the clinical and public health impact of antimicrobial resistance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This study was conducted as a prospective laboratory-based investigation over a defined study period. Clinical samples were collected from patients presenting to tertiary-care hospitals and affiliated diagnostic laboratories. The study focused on the isolation, identification, and antimicrobial susceptibility profiling of Gram-negative bacterial pathogens, with particular emphasis on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. All laboratory procedures were performed in accordance with standard microbiological guidelines and biosafety protocols.

Sample Collection and Processing

A total of 200 non-duplicate clinical specimens were included in the study. Samples were obtained from patients with suspected bacterial infections and comprised urine, blood, sputum, wound swabs, pus, and other relevant clinical materials as requested by the treating physicians. Each specimen was collected using sterile techniques and transported promptly to the microbiology laboratory to minimize contamination and ensure sample integrity.

Upon receipt, samples were logged and processed immediately. Liquid specimens were mixed gently, while swab-based samples were inoculated directly onto culture media. Blood samples were processed using standard blood culture techniques prior to subculture on solid media.

Isolation and Culture of Bacterial Isolates

Primary isolation was carried out by inoculating clinical specimens onto appropriate culture media, including MacConkey agar and Blood agar plates. The inoculated plates were incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 18–24 hours. Plates were examined for bacterial growth, colony morphology, lactose fermentation, hemolytic patterns, and pigment production.

Presumptive identification of Gram-negative organisms was based on colony characteristics observed on MacConkey agar. Non-lactose fermenting colonies with characteristic pigmentation were

suspected as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while lactose-fermenting colonies were further evaluated for *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Pure isolates were obtained by subculturing representative colonies and preserved for further analysis.

Microscopic Examination and Preliminary Identification

All isolates were subjected to Gram staining to confirm Gram-negative bacilli morphology. Microscopic examination was performed under oil immersion to assess cellular shape, arrangement, and staining characteristics. Oxidase testing was performed for preliminary differentiation, particularly to identify *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which demonstrated a positive oxidase reaction.

Motility testing was conducted using standard methods where required. *Escherichia coli* isolates demonstrated active motility, while *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates were identified as non-motile organisms, aiding in differentiation.

Biochemical Characterization

Definitive identification of bacterial isolates was achieved using a series of conventional biochemical tests. These included catalase test, indole production, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, citrate utilization, urease test, triple sugar iron (TSI) agar reactions, and oxidative-fermentative tests where appropriate. Each test was performed according to standard laboratory protocols, and results were interpreted using established identification criteria.

Escherichia coli was confirmed by positive indole and methyl red reactions with negative citrate and urease tests. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was identified by positive citrate and urease reactions, negative indole test, and characteristic mucoid colonies. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was confirmed by oxidase positivity, non-fermentative metabolism, pigment production, and growth at elevated temperatures.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar. A standardized bacterial suspension equivalent to 0.5 McFarland turbidity

was prepared for each isolate. The suspension was evenly inoculated onto Mueller-Hinton agar plates using sterile swabs to ensure uniform lawn growth.

Antibiotic discs representing commonly prescribed antimicrobial classes were placed on the inoculated plates using sterile forceps. Plates were incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 16–18 hours. Following incubation, zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters using a calibrated ruler. Interpretation of susceptibility results was carried out according to the latest Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. Isolates were categorized as susceptible, intermediate, or resistant based on zone diameter breakpoints. Quality control strains were used periodically to ensure accuracy and reproducibility of results.

Data Collection and Management

Demographic and clinical information of patients, including age, gender, specimen type, and clinical diagnosis, was recorded using a structured data collection form. Each isolate was assigned a unique identification code to maintain confidentiality and ensure traceability. Laboratory findings were entered into a dedicated database and cross-checked for accuracy before analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Collected data were analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize frequencies, percentages, and distributions of bacterial isolates and resistance patterns. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation where applicable. Comparative analysis was performed to assess differences in antimicrobial resistance among the studied organisms. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Distribution of Bacterial Isolates from Clinical Samples

A total of 200 clinical specimens were processed during the study period. Gram-negative bacterial growth was confirmed in all included samples. Among the isolates, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas*

aeruginosa, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were the predominant pathogens identified. *E. coli* was the most frequently isolated organism, followed by *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae*. Mixed infections involving more than one organism were observed in 42 (21.0%) samples.

The majority of isolates were recovered from urine and wound-related specimens, followed by sputum and blood samples.

Fig1: Growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

The overall distribution highlights the clinical relevance of these organisms in both community- and hospital-acquired infections.

Table 1. Distribution of bacterial isolates among 200 clinical samples

Bacterial species	Number of isolates (n)	Percentage (%)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	92	46.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	58	29.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	50	25.0
Total	200	100

Fig 2. Showing the Percentage of clinical isolates

Descriptive statistics were generated using SPSS version 25.0. Frequency distributions demonstrated a statistically significant predominance of *E. coli* among the isolated pathogens (χ^2 test, $p < 0.05$).

Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Patient demographic data were analyzed to evaluate associations between infection patterns and host-related factors. The study population included patients from a wide age range, with a higher proportion of infections observed among adults aged 31–60 years. Male patients constituted a slightly higher proportion of cases compared to females. Specimen type analysis revealed that urinary tract samples were significantly associated with *E. coli*, while *P. aeruginosa* was more commonly isolated from wound and respiratory samples.

Table 2. Patient demographics and clinical characteristics (n = 200)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	118	59.0
	Female	82	41.0
Age group (years)	≤30	48	24.0
	31-60	104	52.0
	>60	48	24.0
Specimen type	Urine	86	43.0
	Wound/Pus	54	27.0
	Sputum	36	18.0
	Blood	24	12.0
Mixed infections	Present	42	21.0
	Absent	158	79.0

Fig 3: shows frequency and percentage on basis of gender, age, specimen type and Infection

Comparative analysis using Chi-square tests revealed a significant association between specimen type and bacterial species distribution ($p < 0.01$). GraphPad Prism was used to generate bar graphs illustrating isolate frequency across specimen categories.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Patterns

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing revealed marked differences in resistance profiles among the three organisms. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* demonstrated high resistance to fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins, whereas *E. coli* showed significant resistance to ampicillin and ceftriaxone. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* exhibited notable resistance to cephalosporins and moderate resistance to carbapenems.

Overall, multidrug resistance (defined as resistance to three or more antibiotic classes) was observed in 61.5% of isolates, with the highest prevalence among *P. aeruginosa*. Statistical comparison of resistance rates was performed using one-way ANOVA in SPSS, followed by post-hoc analysis, which revealed significant differences among the three organisms ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Antimicrobial resistance patterns of major isolates

Antibiotic	<i>E. coli</i> (%)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (%)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (%)	p-value
Ampicillin	78.3	NA	74.0	<0.001
Ceftriaxone	62.0	69.0	66.0	0.002
Ciprofloxacin	54.3	71.0	58.0	<0.001
Gentamicin	39.1	48.3	44.0	0.010
Imipenem	12.0	28.0	24.0	<0.001

Fig 4: Antimicrobial resistance pattern of isolates

Fig 5: Measurement of resistance and sensitivity patterns

Resistance trends were visualized using clustered bar charts generated in GraphPad Prism, allowing direct comparison of antimicrobial performance across organisms.

The results demonstrate a high burden of Gram-negative bacterial infections with substantial antimicrobial resistance. The predominance of *E. coli*, followed by *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae*, reflects their clinical significance in diverse infection sites. The high rate of multidrug resistance,

particularly among *P. aeruginosa*, underscores the urgent need for antimicrobial stewardship and continuous resistance surveillance.

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates a substantial burden of antimicrobial resistance among clinically important Gram-negative pathogens, with *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* identified as the predominant isolates from a range of clinical specimens. These findings are consistent with global and regional surveillance data indicating that these organisms are major contributors to both community- and hospital-acquired infections and are increasingly associated with multidrug resistance (Asghar, Zaidi, Tariq, & Ain, 2025).

In this study, *E. coli* was the most frequently isolated pathogen, reflecting its well-established role as a leading cause of urinary tract and bloodstream infections. Comparable prevalence rates have been reported in recent studies from South Asia and other low- and middle-income regions, where *E. coli* accounts for nearly half of Gram-negative clinical isolates (Tanni et al., 2025). The high resistance observed to commonly used antibiotics, including β -lactams and fluoroquinolones, aligns with reports describing the widespread dissemination of extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing *E. coli*. These resistance trends pose a significant challenge to empirical therapy and highlight the consequences of antibiotic misuse and limited stewardship in many healthcare settings (Ali et al., 2025).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa exhibited the highest overall resistance rates in the present study, consistent with its intrinsic resistance mechanisms and capacity to acquire additional resistance determinants. Similar resistance patterns have been documented globally, particularly in hospital environments where selective antibiotic pressure is high. The ability of *P. aeruginosa* to form biofilms and survive under adverse conditions further complicates treatment and contributes to persistent infections (Bilal, Khan, Shafiq, Farooq, & Khan, 2025). Our findings reinforce existing evidence that *P. aeruginosa* remains one of the most difficult Gram-negative pathogens to manage clinically, especially in resource-limited settings.

Klebsiella pneumoniae also demonstrated notable resistance to multiple antimicrobial classes, in agreement with recent studies reporting increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant and carbapenem-resistant strains. The encapsulated nature of *K. pneumoniae*, combined with its capacity to harbor and disseminate resistance genes, makes it a significant threat in healthcare facilities. Regional surveillance data from Pakistan and neighboring countries similarly report high resistance rates among *K. pneumoniae*, particularly to cephalosporins and other broad-spectrum agents, underscoring the urgent need for enhanced infection control measures (Ali et al., 2025).

Comparative analysis of resistance patterns among the three organisms revealed statistically significant differences, emphasizing the importance of organism-specific susceptibility data for guiding treatment decisions. The high proportion of multidrug-resistant isolates observed in this study is consistent with recent national and international reports and reflects the growing AMR crisis in developing healthcare systems. Limited access to diagnostic facilities, delayed initiation of appropriate therapy, and inconsistent antimicrobial policies likely contribute to these trends.

Overall, the findings of this study underscore the critical need for continuous local surveillance of antimicrobial resistance, implementation of robust antimicrobial stewardship programs, and strengthening of infection prevention strategies. Regular updating of institutional antibiograms and rational antibiotic prescribing are essential to curb the spread of resistance. Further multicenter studies incorporating molecular characterization of resistance mechanisms are recommended to better understand transmission dynamics and inform targeted interventions.

CONCLUSION

This study provides important insight into the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance patterns of major Gram-negative bacterial pathogens, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, isolated from clinical specimens. The findings demonstrate a high burden of multidrug resistance among these organisms, with *E. coli* emerging as the most frequently isolated pathogen, while *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae* exhibited comparatively higher resistance to

multiple antimicrobial classes. These resistance profiles highlight the increasing difficulty of managing common bacterial infections using standard empirical treatment regimens.

The observed resistance trends are consistent with regional and global reports, reflecting the widespread misuse of antibiotics, inadequate infection control practices, and limited implementation of antimicrobial stewardship programs. The presence of mixed infections and the significant association between specimen type and bacterial distribution further emphasize the clinical complexity of Gram-negative infections in healthcare settings. These findings underscore the necessity of routine antimicrobial susceptibility testing to guide targeted therapy and minimize treatment failure.

From a public health perspective, the results emphasize the urgent need for strengthened surveillance systems, regular updating of local antibiograms, and enforcement of rational antibiotic prescribing practices. Integrating laboratory-based resistance data into clinical decision-making can improve patient outcomes and reduce the spread of resistant strains. Future studies incorporating molecular characterization and multicenter data are recommended to better understand resistance mechanisms and transmission dynamics. Collectively, these efforts are essential to mitigate the growing threat of antimicrobial resistance and preserve the effectiveness of existing antimicrobial agents.

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